

ABSTRACT

The beginning and the end of a microbial community and their carbohydrate-active enzymes at a thermophilic composting

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Composting harbors a rich microbial diversity and is a source of potential microbial candidates and enzymes for lignocellulosic degradation that can be of interest for industrial, clinical, environmental, and biotechnological applications. Our goal is to analyze this microbial diversity focusing on metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) recovered from the beginning (inoculum) and the end (mature compost) of the composting process and genes annotated for carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes). We collected five samples from inoculum (ZCI) and two from mature compost (ZMC) in the composting facility at the São Paulo Zoo Park. Inoculum consists of a compost pile in a later phase of the composting process that is extracted and added to alternate layers of plant and animal waste to start a new composting pile. Mature compost is the product of the composting process ready to be used as fertilizer. Total DNA was sequenced with Illumina technology. ZCI reads were co-assembled using metaSPAdes. We used the metaWRAP pipeline for MAG recovery with three binners: MetaBAT2, MaxBin2, and Concoct. All the bins were consolidated using the bin_refinement module from the metaWRAP pipeline with minimum completeness of 50% and maximum contamination of 10%. We used the same method to recover MAGs from ZMC. MAGs were taxonomically classified using GTDB-tk and annotated for CAZymes using dbcan2. We also used dbcan2 for contigs not included in MAGs. From the total of ~7,4 million reads for ZCI and ~6,8 million reads for ZMC, we obtained respectively 500,267 (N50=1349) and 399,726 (N50=1584) contigs for ZCI and ZMC. We retrieved 22 and 20 MAGs respectively for ZCI and ZMC. For ZCI MAGs, we found 891 hits for CAZymes distributed in 138 CAZY families, while for ZMC MAGs, 1141 hits were distributed in 176 families. For ZCI contigs not included in MAGs, 2437 hits for CAZymes were distributed in 218 CAZY families while for ZMC, 2206 hits were distributed in 220 families. Therefore, we were able to obtain a catalog of CAZymes for MAGs and contigs not included in MAGs from the inoculum and the mature compost of the Sao Paulo Zoo composting, comprising cellulases, hemicellulases, xylanases, and manases. These results reinforce the composting as a source of potential microbial candidates for lignocellulose degradation and other analysis is ongoing for further understanding of the composting microbiology.

Keywords: Metagenomics; MAG Recovery; Bacteria; Plant Waste; Organic Matter.

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